

no functional resistance (IR8 and TN1). When rices with adult plant resistance (IR1698 and IR944) were infected at tillering stage (45 days after seeding), lesion length did not differ from that on rices (IR8) with no resistance to pathotypes 1 and 2. High nitrogen levels did not affect lesion length on varieties

with specific resistance. But lesion length increased if the variety-pathotype combination was compatible (i.e. the varieties' resistance was overcome by pathotypes of different virulence). Thus, when IR20 was infected with pathotype 1 (to which it is resistant), lesion length did not significantly increase. But when

infection was caused by Pathotype 2 (to which IR20 is susceptible), lesion length increased proportionally with increased nitrogen. When IR1545-339 was infected with both pathotypes (to which the breeding line was resistant), lesion length did not increase. ■

Effect of fungicides on the inactivation of sclerotia and mycelia of *Rhizoctonia solani*

S. Kannaiyan and N. N. Prasad, Microbiology Laboratory, Agriculture College, Annamalai University, Annamalai Nagar 608101, Tamil Nadu, India

Sheath blight disease caused by *Rhizoctonia solani* is severe in many rice-growing areas of Tamil Nadu. The effect of certain fungicides on the viability of sclerotia and mycelia of *R. solani* was studied.

Soil was well sieved and air-dried, then placed in 25-ml vials and autoclaved for 1 hour at 15 lb. An 8-mm agar disc of the pathogen was placed on the soil and then covered with 2.5 cm sterilized soil. Similarly sclerotia were placed on the soil surface of another set of vials and covered with soil.

The fungicides Bavistin, Benlate, Demosan, Hinosan, wettable Ceresan, Brassicol, Kitazin, Vitavax, and thiabendazole were tested at 0.05, 0.1, and 0.2% levels. Five milliliters of each fungicidal solution was applied to the soil surface with a pipette. The vials were incubated for 24 hours at room temperature. Then they were emptied and the soil was washed off with running water. The mycelial discs and sclerotia were removed with sterile forceps, plated on Czapek's agar medium, and observed for viability.

All the fungicides except wettable Ceresan completely inhibited mycelial growth at all the concentrations. Hinosan, Kitazin, and Vitavax completely inhibited sclerotial germination at all concentrations. Bavistin at 0.2% inhibited sclerotial germination. Benlate, Demosan, Brassicol, thiabendazole, and wettable Ceresan did not effectively inhibit sclerotial germination. ■

In vitro* effect of certain fungicides on the growth and sclerotial production of *Rhizoctonia solani

S. Kannaiyan and N. N. Prasad, Microbiology Laboratory, Agriculture College, Annamalai University, Annamalai Nagar 6081 01, Tamil Nadu, India

Sheath blight disease of rice caused by *Rhizoctonia solani* is serious in Tamilnadu. The efficacy of certain fungicides against *R. solani* was tested. The fungicides EL-273, N.F. 48, Bavistin, Vitavax, Difolatan, Agallol, Plantvax, Benlate, Agrosan GN, Fytolan, Brestan, Brassicol, thiabendazole, Hinosan, Kitazin, Daconil, Demosan, Macuprax, wettable Ceresan, Dithane D-14, Dithane M-45, Dexon, captan, thiram, and Dithane Z-78 were

incorporated in Czapek's medium at 0.025%, 0.05%, 0.1%, and 0.2% levels. The medium was seeded with *R. solani*. After 15 days of incubation the dry weight of the fungus was determined.

All of the fungicides tested inhibited the pathogen growth at all concentrations. The fungicides N.F. 48, Bavistin, Vitavax, Benlate, Brassicol, thiabendazole, Hinosan, Kitazin, Daconil, and Demosan completely arrested growth and sclerotial production, even at 0.025%. On the other hand, Agallol, EL-273, Agrosan, Dexon, captan, and thiram completely inhibited the growth and sclerotial production of the pathogen only at the 0.2% level. The other fungicides decreased growth as concentration was increased. ■

Root injury and kresek development on rice

B. A. Zaragoza and T. W. Mew, Plant Pathology Department, International Rice Research Institute

In the field, kresek infection on rice plants usually occurs 1 to 6 weeks after transplanting. An early study suggested that root injury is related to kresek infection. In this study, kresek developed on seedlings raised in a seedbed infested with bacterial cells of *Xanthomonas oryzae*. The percentage of kresek was high when the seedbox was infested near transplanting time, but was minimal when the seedbed was infested at the time of sowing and the seedlings were transplanted 21 days later.

More kresek was produced in transplanted than in direct-seeded rice when the seedbox soil was infested with the bacterial pathogen by incorporating bacterial suspension at different concentrations. The percentage of kresek

infection and inoculum dosages were linearly correlated in transplanted rice.

Two types of seedbeds were compared. In the ordinary seedbed, kresek incidence was similar regardless of whether the roots of seedlings were injured by clipping or not. Among seedlings raised in the dapog bed, those with uninjured roots had considerably less kresek infection than those with injured roots. ■

Seed pathology of rice in Indonesia, 1975-78

J. Supriaman and L. T. Palmer, Plant Pathology Section, Central Research Institute for Agriculture, Sukamandi Branch, Sukamandi, W. Java, Indonesia

The fungi incidence was analyzed in 133 seed samples of rice from Java, Bali, and South Sulawesi (Indonesia) from 1975 to 1978. The samples were obtained from 13 commercial and 40 local varieties or promising lines. Fifteen fungal genera and

21 species were isolated through standard seed pathology techniques. The most common were *Trichoconis padwickii*, *Drechslera oryzae*, *Curvularia lunata*,

and *Fusarium semitectum* in 86, 78, 77 and 65% of the samples, respectively. Varietal differences in the fungi isolated were noted. IR26 and C4-63 had lower-

incidence than the other cultivars; IR5 had higher. Kernel smut *Tilletia barclayana* was isolated from seven lines grown in a Central Java nursery in 1977. ■

Pest management and control

INSECTS

Major insect pests of rainfed wetland rice in tropical Asia

Summarized by J. A. Litsinger, Cropping Systems Program, International Rice Research Institute

Rice is a highly adaptable crop and is cultivated over a wide range of environments. Rice culture is classified

on the basis of water availability into four major environments: 1) deep water, 2) irrigated wetland, 3) rainfed wetland, and 4) dryland. Within tropical Asia, rice entomology research has concentrated on irrigated wetland and dryland environments, and little attention has been given to deepwater and rainfed wetland environments.

Recent statistics show that the rainfed wetland environment occupies 46% of the land area devoted to rice in Asia exclusive of the People's Republic of China. Within this classification rice is usually grown as a single crop during the monsoon season and is subject to periodic and unpredictable drought and flooding. These areas are typified by a

Insect pests of rainfed wetland rice in tropical Asia as determined by a survey of rice entomologists,^a 1978.

Pest ^b		Country ^c							
Scientific name	Common name	Bangladesh	Burma	India	Indonesia	Malaysia	Philippines	Sri Lanka	Thailand
<i>Tryporyza incertulas</i> (Walker)	Yellow rice borer	**	**	**	**		**		*
<i>T. innotata</i> (Walker)	White rice borer			*	**		**	0	
<i>T. nivella</i> (Fabricius)	Top borer	0				0		0	*
<i>Chilo suppressalis</i> (Walker)	Striped rice borer		*	*	*		*		*
<i>C. polychrysus</i> (Meyrick)	Dark-headed rice borer	*				*			**
<i>Sesamia inferens</i> (Walker)	Pink borer	*		*		*	*		
<i>Orseolia oryzae</i> (Wood-Mason)	Rice gall midge	*		**	**	0	0	**	**
<i>Nymphula depunctalis</i> Guenee	Rice caseworm	*	*	**	**	*	**	*	*
<i>Cnaphalocrosis medinalis</i> (Guenee)	Rice leaf folder	*		**	**	*	**	**	**
<i>Mythimna separata</i> (Walker)	Rice ear-cutting caterpillar	*	*	*	*		*		*
<i>Spodoptera mauritia</i> (Boisduval)	Rice swarming caterpillar			**	**		*		**
<i>Pelopidas mathias</i> (Fabricius)	Rice skipper			*	*				*
<i>Melanitis leda ismene</i> Cramer	Rice green-horned caterpillar			*	*		*		*
<i>Rivula near atimeta</i> Swinhoe	Rice hairy caterpillar	0	0	0	0	0	*	0	0
<i>Susumia exigua</i> (Butler)	Fijian leaf folder	0				0		0	*
<i>Leptocoris acuta</i> Thunberg	Rice bug	*	*		**		**	*	**
<i>L. oratorius</i> (Fabricius)	Rice bug	*	*		**	*	**	0	**
<i>Scotinophora coarctata</i> (Fabricius)	Malayan black rice bug					*		0	*
<i>S. lurida</i> (Burmeister)	Japanese black rice bug				*			*	*
<i>Hieroglyphus banian</i> (Fabricius)	Large rice grasshopper			*	*	0			*
<i>Patanga succincta</i> (Linnaeus)	Bombay locust	0		*	*			0	*
<i>Locusta migratoria manilensis</i> (Meyen)	Oriental migratory locust	0		*	*			0	*
<i>Oxya chinensis</i> (Thunberg)	Small rice grasshopper			*	*			0	*
<i>Nephotettix virescens</i> (Distant)	Green rice leafhopper	*		*	*	*	*		*
<i>N. nigropictus</i> (Stal)	Green rice leafhopper	*		*	*		*		*
<i>Recilia dorsalis</i> (Motschulsky)	Zig-zag rice leafhopper			*	*			*	*
<i>Nilaparvata lugens</i> (Stål)	Brown rice planthopper			**	**	*		**	*
<i>Sogatella furcifera</i> (Horvath)	Whitebacked rice planthopper			*	*	*		*	*
<i>Hydrellia</i> spp.	Rice whorl maggot			*	*		**		*
<i>Atherigona oryzae</i> (=exigua) Stein	Rice shoot fly			*	*			*	*
<i>Baliothrips biformis</i> (Bugnall)	Rice thrips			*		0	0	**	*
<i>Brevinnia rehi</i> (Lindinger)	Rice mealy bug			*		0		0	*
<i>Dicladispa armigera</i> (Oliver)	Rice hispa	*		*		0	0		*
<i>Echinocnemus oryzae</i> (Marshall)	Rice root weevil	0		*		0	0	0	

^aBangladesh (S. Alam, H.D. Catling, A.N.M. Rezaul Karim), Burma (U Mya Thwin), India (N. Panda, K.C. Mathur), Indonesia (I. Manwan, A. Kartohardjono, O. Mochida), Malaysia (G.S. Lim), Philippines (J.A. Litsinger), Sri Lanka (N. Wickremasinghe), Thailand (W. Katanyukul, S. Pongprasert). ^bPawar, A.D. 1975. The rice Entomology Newsletter No. 2. Updated by A.T. Barrion, Entomology Department, IRRI. ^c** = major insect (perennial yield losses of 5% in at least 1 major region within the country), * = minor pest (variable year-to-year infestations resulting in yield losses of 5% in at least 1 major region within a country), 0 = pest not recorded on rice from the country.